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Review Article

A Comprehensive Review of Alzheimer's Disease: Pathogenesis, Clinical Manifestations, And Therapeutic Strategies

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder and the leading cause of dementia globally. This review provides a detailed examination of the epidemiology of AD, focusing on incidence, prevalence, and risk factors such as age, genetics, and lifestyle. The clinical manifestations are explored across different stages, from mild cognitive impairment to severe dementia, with emphasis on memory loss, behavioural changes, and functional decline. Diagnostic tools, including neuroimaging, cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers, and cognitive tests, are critically reviewed for their role in early detection. The pathophysiology of AD is discussed, highlighting amyloid- β plaques, tau tangles, oxidative stress, and neuroinflammation. Genetic mutations in genes such as APP, PSEN1, PSEN2, and APOE are reviewed to understand their role in familial and sporadic cases of AD. Current therapeutic approaches, including cholinesterase inhibitors and NMDA receptor antagonists, are evaluated, alongside novel strategies like enzyme replacement therapy, gene therapy etc. The review also explores various plant-based compounds and marketed formulations, such as curcumin, ginkgo biloba, and huperzine A, assessing their neuroprotective properties and clinical efficacy in mitigating AD progression. This comprehensive review aims to offer insights into current and emerging treatments for AD, including the potential of natural compounds in disease management.

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder marked by extensive neuronal loss, particularly in the cerebral cortex and hippocampus. It is neuropathologically defined by the extracellular accumulation of amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plaques and intracellular

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neurofibrillary tangles of hyperphosphorylated tau protein. A β is generated via proteolytic cleavage of amyloid precursor protein (APP) by γ - and β -secretases, including presenilin 1 (PS1) and PS2. Pathological changes begin in the frontal and temporal lobes, later involving other neocortical areas [1]. AD's clinical course spans 8-10 years, often preceded by decades-long preclinical and prodromal phases. Sporadic AD, accounting for most cases, typically manifests in the eighth decade of life, often due to impaired A β clearance. In contrast, autosomal dominant inherited AD (DIAD), caused by APP, PS1, and PS2 mutations, accounts for <1% of cases, with onset around 45 years. Both forms share similar clinical and biomarker profiles, despite differing etiologies [2]. AD's pathogenesis is multifactorial, with A β accumulation as a central feature. However, therapeutic interventions targeting A β have failed to provide substantial clinical benefits, leaving no disease-modifying treatments available. Current pharmacotherapies, including cholinesterase inhibitors and memantine, primarily manage symptoms, offering modest cognitive improvement. Tailored symptomatic treatment can significantly enhance patient quality of life by prolonging independence and delaying institutional care. AD shares overlapping features with other neurodegenerative disorders, such as Parkinson's disease and frontotemporal dementia, raising questions about its distinctiveness versus its potential as a byproduct of aging. The coexistence of comorbidities, including cerebrovascular disease and hippocampal sclerosis, further complicates diagnosis and management in elderly patients [3]. Despite the lack of novel FDA-approved drugs since 2003, ongoing research has advanced understanding of AD's pathophysiology, aiding in the refinement of

therapeutic strategies. This review examines the epidemiology, molecular mechanisms, diagnostic advances, preventive measures, and therapeutic approaches for AD, emphasizing the need for personalized treatment to optimize outcomes.

Objective: This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of Alzheimer's disease (AD), focusing on its epidemiology, clinical manifestations, risk factors, and pathophysiological mechanisms. It explores genetic mutations, current diagnostic approaches, and therapeutic options. Additionally, the review discusses dietary management strategies and the potential role of gene therapy in AD treatment. By synthesizing recent research, the review seeks to advance understanding and inform future therapeutic and research directions for AD.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The literature review for this article on Alzheimer's disease (AD) was conducted through extensive searches in scientific electronic databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, Web of Science, ACS Publications, Science Direct, Taylor and Francis, Wiley, Springer, and SCOPUS.

3. Epidemiology

Global Perspective: Alzheimer's disease (AD) affects a significant portion of the global population, with 47 million cases reported in 2015, representing approximately 5% of the elderly population [4]. This number is expected to increase to 75 million by 2030 and 132 million by 2050, driven primarily by population aging. Each year, nearly 9.9 million new cases are diagnosed worldwide, equating to one new case every three seconds. A disproportionate burden is seen in low- and middle-income countries, currently accounting for 60% of cases, with this share projected to rise to 71% by 2050 [5,6]. (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Here is a bar graph depicting the number of people suffering from Alzheimer's Disease in the world from 2010 to 2024. The graph shows a steady increase in the number of cases over the years, highlighting the growing prevalence of Alzheimer's Disease in the world. Indian Perspective: Alzheimer's disease has thus gradually gained place as one of the most critical issues related to public health in India and houses the second-oldest population in the world. Today, an estimated 4.1 million are reported to suffer from dementia, which also includes Alzheimer's disease [7]. These figures are likely to rise more than double by 2030 due to demographic trends and

changes in life expectancy. In the age group 65+, the prevalence of dementia ranges from 1.5% to 2%, showing significant inequalities which are influenced by geographic and demographic features [8]. However, the actual disease burden is probably underestimated due to a variety of barriers. Stigma regarding culture, lack of awareness, and less availability of diagnostic resources causes broad underdiagnosis, with ensuing delay in treatment and care. Symptoms of Alzheimer's disease is always misunderstood as normal aging characteristics that prevent timely intervention. (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Here is a bar graph depicting the number of people suffering from Alzheimer's Disease in India from 2010 to 2024. The graph shows a steady increase in the number of cases over the years, highlighting the growing prevalence of Alzheimer's Disease in India.

4. Clinical Manifestation

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by a

range of cognitive, functional, and behavioural impairments. It is the most common cause of dementia, particularly in the elderly, and is marked by a distinct clinical course.

4.1. Early Stage:

In the initial stages, AD manifests primarily as subtle cognitive impairments. Episodic memory deficits, such as forgetting recent events or conversations, are common, while older memories

remain preserved. Patients may exhibit mild language disturbances, including difficulty in word retrieval (anomia), and visuospatial challenges, such as trouble navigating familiar environments. Early executive dysfunctions, including reduced attention and impaired planning, may also appear [9].

4.2. Moderate Stage:

As AD progresses, cognitive impairments become more pronounced. Memory loss extends to remote memories, and language disturbances, such as paraphasias, are more evident. Patients may experience apraxia (difficulty with purposeful movements) and agnosia (inability to recognize objects or people). Behavioral and psychiatric symptoms, including apathy, depression, agitation, and sleep disturbances, emerge during this stage. Disorientation to time and place is common, increasing the risk of wandering or becoming lost [10].

4.3. Late Stage:

Advanced AD is marked by severe cognitive and motor decline. Patients lose the ability to recognize close family members (severe agnosia) and may become mute. Motor impairments, including severe apraxia and gait disturbances, are prominent, leading to an increased risk of falls. Dependence on caregivers becomes total, as basic activities of daily living (ADLs) cannot be performed [11].

4.4. Terminal Stage:

In the final stage, patients are bedridden and entirely dependent. Dysphagia, pressure ulcers, and infections, including aspiration pneumonia, are common complications and frequent causes of death. The terminal phase concludes with multi-system decline, emphasizing the need for palliative care [12].

5. Diagnosis And Risk Factors

The diagnosis process for Alzheimer's disease includes a number of steps. It begins with a comprehensive medical history, including

background, family history, and progression of symptoms. Neuropsychological evaluations help quantify cognitive impairments, distinguish the cause from other dementias, and serve as a baseline for tracking change. Neurological exams are also completed to rule out other conditions that could have similar mimicking effects [13]. Laboratory studies-including blood and metabolic analyses-help identify potential, reversible causes of dementia. Neuroimaging techniques, including MRI, measure atrophy in the brain and differentiate AD from other types of dementias. The comprehensive approach significantly improves early diagnosis and accuracy, ensuring that disease management and care planning can be more effective [14]. Identification of AD is a quite complicated process requiring collaboration with the myriad disciplines. Essentially, the process involves a combination of clinical evaluation, cognitive and neuroimaging tests, and evaluation of biomarkers.

a. Clinical Assessment:

Medical history: It will include detailed assessment of cognitive symptoms, behavioral changes, and functional impairment. Such tests would include cognitive assessment, which is mostly standardized measures of the MMSE and MoCA, the most commonly used tests for quantifying cognitive decline [15].

b. Neuroimaging:

Atrophy is identifiable within the hippocampus and many other areas of the brain, which are characterized by morphological changes, through magnetic resonance imaging.

- **Amyloid PET:** Is sensitive to visualizing the amyloid-beta plaques, which are hallmark for AD [16].
- **Tau PET:** Shows deposition of tau protein, which is a major pathological marker.
- **FDG-PET:** Evaluate glucose metabolism in the brain to assess metabolic disorder.

- **Computed Tomography (CT):** Although less sensitive than MRI, CT scans can be used to rule out other causes of dementia, such as stroke or tumors [17].

c. Biomarker Analysis:

Cerebrospinal Fluid: Biomarker evaluation in cerebrospinal fluid such as amyloid-beta A β 42, total tau t-tau and phosphorylated tau p-tau can give important diagnostic information regarding AD pathology. Recent research has made available promising biomarkers that are derived from blood, which include the plasma A β 42/A β 40 ratio and p-tau181 and neurofilament light chain (NfL) [18].

d. Neuropsychological Evaluation:

Neuropsychological assessment is an exploration including all findings on memory, attention, execution functioning, language, and visuospatial skills [19].

e. Genetic Testing:

Genetic testing may be recommended for individuals with a strong family history of Alzheimer's disease, particularly early-onset cases. The most common genetic markers associated with AD include mutations in the amyloid precursor protein (APP) gene, presenilin 1 (PSEN1) gene, and presenilin 2 (PSEN2) gene [20,21].

f. Differential Diagnosis:

Given the overlap of symptoms with other neurodegenerative diseases, a differential diagnosis is essential. Conditions such as Lewy body dementia, frontotemporal dementia, and vascular dementia must be considered. This process often involves ruling out other causes of

cognitive decline through a combination of the aforementioned techniques [22].

Risk factors

Neurological and neurodegenerative diseases, like Alzheimer's, are the culmination of associated factors. Oxidative stress and chronic inflammation are significantly associated with the destruction of neuronal cells and an increase in neurodegenerative processes. Genetic predisposition to these diseases through inheritance can be significant; examples include mutations in genes, specifically the APOE, that significantly increase a person's risk of developing such diseases [23]. The risk also increases with age due to inevitable structural and functional deterioration in cerebral activity. Cardiovascular health significantly influences cognitive performance since diseases such as hypertension and atherosclerosis reduce cerebral blood flow and enhance the possibility of cognitive decline. In addition, head injury from accidents causes continued damage to neural tissue and makes it more susceptible to degradation [24]. Lastly, lifestyle is the most significant, because habits such as smoking, excessive drinking, and unhealthy eating affect the brain adversely, while regular physical activity and healthy lifestyles add protective effects. Permanent damage to the normal functions of the neurological system is a result of interaction with environmental toxins, heavy metals, and industrial pollutants. Mental health issues such as chronic stress, depression disorders, and insomnia break down resistance in the brain and accelerate cognitive decline (Fig. 3) [25].

Fig. 3: This figure depicts the various risk factors that contribute to the development of Alzheimer's Disease.

6. Pathophysiology

6.1. Molecular and Cellular Mechanism:

6.1.1. Amyloid β Hypothesis

The amyloid hypothesis, proposed by Hardy and Higgins, highlights amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) peptide accumulation as central to Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathogenesis [26]. Supporting this theory is the overrepresentation of AD in individuals with Down syndrome, attributed to amyloid precursor protein (APP) overexpression from trisomy 21. In AD, amyloidosis manifests as extracellular deposition of insoluble amyloid fibrils in the brain, forming senile plaques that disrupt neuronal function and drive disease progression [27,28]. APP, a type I transmembrane protein, plays a dual role: it participates in physiological processes like neuronal development and synaptic plasticity and serves as the precursor for $A\beta$. Proteolytic cleavage of APP occurs via two pathways: the amyloidogenic pathway, mediated by β - and γ -secretase, generates $A\beta$ peptides prone to aggregation, especially $A\beta_{42}$. An imbalance between $A\beta$ production and clearance leads to its

accumulation, forming neurotoxic oligomers and fibrils. Soluble $A\beta$ oligomers are particularly harmful, disrupting synaptic function and contributing to oxidative stress, inflammation, and mitochondrial dysfunction [29,30]. While the amyloid hypothesis provides a foundational framework for AD research, it is now recognized as an oversimplification. The amyloid cascade hypothesis suggests a progression from $A\beta$ accumulation to neurofibrillary tangles, neuronal loss, and dementia. However, this model does not fully explain AD's heterogeneity, variable correlation between $A\beta$ burden and symptoms, or the limited success of anti-amyloid therapies in delivering cognitive benefits [31]. Challenges to the amyloid hypothesis include the inconsistent relationship between $A\beta$ pathology and clinical symptoms; some individuals with high $A\beta$ loads remain asymptomatic, while others develop severe dementia with lower $A\beta$ levels. This underscores the influence of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors in AD progression. Moreover, anti-amyloid therapies have shown limited clinical efficacy, questioning the sufficiency of targeting $A\beta$ alone as a therapeutic approach (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: The amyloidogenic pathway in Alzheimer's disease involves the breakdown of amyloid precursor protein (APP) by specific enzymes. Initially, beta-secretase cleaves APP within the membrane, followed by gamma-secretase, producing extracellular amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) peptides. These peptides are prone to self-assembly, forming toxic oligomers and insoluble $A\beta$ fibrils, which contribute to the formation of amyloid plaques and the progression of the disease.

6.1.2. $A\beta$ Receptor Interactions and Synaptic Dysfunction

The mechanisms by which amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) induces synaptic dysfunction remain a complex and evolving research area. Emerging evidence points to the involvement of specific receptor systems in mediating $A\beta$'s deleterious effects [32]. The immune inhibitory receptor L1rB2, traditionally linked to immune regulation, has been implicated in Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathogenesis. L1rB2 binds $A\beta$ oligomers, potentially contributing to synaptic dysfunction through microglial activation and complement system pathways. This interplay between inflammation and neurodegeneration highlights its relevance in AD progression [33]. The N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDAR), a key glutamate receptor for synaptic plasticity, is also implicated in $A\beta$ -induced excitotoxicity. $A\beta$ disrupts NMDAR function, causing excessive calcium influx, which triggers oxidative stress,

mitochondrial dysfunction, and pro-apoptotic pathways. These effects culminate in neuronal damage and synaptic loss. The cellular prion protein (PrPc) has been identified as another receptor for $A\beta$ oligomers, contributing to synaptic impairment and cognitive decline. $A\beta$ -PrPc interactions may activate intracellular signaling pathways that disrupt cytoskeletal integrity and impair synaptic plasticity [34]. Additionally, Eph receptor tyrosine kinases, particularly EphB2 and EphA4, have emerged as mediators of $A\beta$ -induced synaptic changes. These receptors are critical for dendritic spine morphology and synaptic plasticity. $A\beta$ -driven dysregulation of Eph signaling may disrupt synaptic formation, leading to cognitive deficits. These findings underscore the multifaceted role of $A\beta$ in synaptic dysfunction. Understanding the molecular interactions between $A\beta$ and these receptor systems is crucial for developing targeted therapies to mitigate synaptic loss and cognitive decline in AD [35,36].

6.1.3. Tau Pathology and Neurofibrillary Tangles in Alzheimer's Disease

Tau, a microtubule-associated protein encoded by the MAPT gene on chromosome 17, is primarily localized in neuronal axons, where it plays a vital role in stabilizing microtubules and facilitating axonal transport and neurite growth [37]. Tau phosphorylation regulates its ability to modulate microtubule dynamics, maintaining the balance between stability and flexibility essential for neuronal

function. However, in Alzheimer's disease (AD), this process becomes dysregulated, leading to tau hyperphosphorylation, which disrupts microtubule integrity and axonal transport, impairing neuronal communication and synaptic function. These deficits contribute to neurodegeneration, a hallmark of AD. Hyperphosphorylated tau undergoes structural changes, aggregating into oligomers, paired helical filaments, and eventually neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs). NFTs, a neuropathological hallmark of AD, correlate strongly with dementia severity. The Braak staging system classifies tau pathology based on its post-mortem distribution, offering insights into disease progression. Tau aggregation disrupts cytoskeletal organization, impairs intracellular transport, and releases neurotoxic substances, exacerbating neuronal loss and brain atrophy [38]. Multiple factors drive tau hyperphosphorylation. Amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plays a significant role by influencing kinase and phosphatase activities. Dysregulated kinases, such as GSK3, CDK5, and

MARK, enhance tau phosphorylation, while compromised phosphatase activity prevents dephosphorylation. Chronic inflammation and oxidative stress further exacerbate this process, linking tau pathology with broader AD mechanisms [39]. NFT formation actively contributes to neurodegeneration by disrupting neuronal architecture and function. Tau pathology initially affects the hippocampus and entorhinal cortex, leading to mild cognitive impairment (MCI). As NFTs spread to the frontal and occipital lobes, cognitive decline worsens, culminating in severe dementia, brain atrophy, and ventricular enlargement [40]. Targeting tau hyperphosphorylation and NFT formation represents a promising therapeutic approach for AD. Strategies aimed at restoring tau homeostasis, inhibiting aggregation, or enhancing clearance mechanisms could potentially mitigate disease progression and preserve cognitive function in patients (Fig. 5) [41].

Fig. 5: This figure shows how the normal function of tau protein in maintaining microtubule stability can be disrupted in pathological conditions due to hyperphosphorylation and aggregation, leading to the formation of NFTs and contributing to the development of neurodegenerative diseases.

6.1.4. Mitochondrial Dysfunction and Oxidative Stress in Alzheimer's Disease

Mitochondria, essential for neuronal energy production, undergo significant dysfunction in Alzheimer's disease (AD), contributing to its

progression. Amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) accumulation within mitochondria disrupts their structure and function, leading to decreased ATP production, reduced respiratory capacity, and impaired energy metabolism, all of which contribute to neuronal dysfunction in AD [42]. In addition to energy deficits, mitochondria are a primary source of reactive oxygen species (ROS). While ROS play physiological roles, their overproduction in AD, exacerbated by $A\beta$, induces oxidative stress. This imbalance causes cellular damage through lipid

peroxidation, protein oxidation, and DNA damage, further compromising mitochondrial and neuronal function [43,44]. Mitochondrial dynamics, including fusion and fission, are also disrupted in AD. A β promotes mitochondrial fragmentation, impairing function and increasing oxidative stress susceptibility. Fusion, which is protective by enabling component exchange and quality control, is diminished. This imbalance in dynamics exacerbates mitochondrial dysfunction and accelerates neurodegeneration in AD

6.1.5. Nitrosative Stress

Nitrosative stress, arising from an imbalance between reactive nitrogen species (RNS) production and cellular defences, is implicated in neurodegenerative processes. Nitric oxide (NO), a primary RNS, functions as a signalling molecule essential for synaptic plasticity, neurotransmission, and brain development. However, in Alzheimer's disease (AD), dysregulated NO production contributes to cognitive decline through mechanisms involving synaptic dysfunction and glial activation [45]. Amyloid-beta (A β)-induced NO generation has been shown to trigger mitochondrial fission via S-nitrosylation, leading to neuronal degeneration. Additionally, elevated S-nitrosothiol-CDK5 levels in AD post-mortem brain tissue compared to healthy controls suggest a critical role for this pathway in disease progression. The pronounced neuronal atrophy and increased S-nitrosylation observed in AD brains provide a foundation for investigating the contribution of S-nitrosylation to nitrosative stress-mediated AD pathogenesis [46].

6.1.6. Protein Oxidation and Lipid Peroxidation

Numerous studies suggest that reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a pivotal role in the development of neurodegeneration in Alzheimer's disease (AD). Over time, the accumulation of ROS and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) leads to oxidative modifications of proteins and the peroxidation of lipids. The brain is particularly susceptible to these oxidative processes due to its high content of unsaturated lipids, elevated levels of metal ions, significant oxygen consumption, and relatively weak antioxidant defense mechanisms. Consequently, the oxidative damage to proteins and lipids poses a significant threat to neuronal integrity.

6.1.7. Glial Cells in Alzheimer's Disease

Neuroinflammation, characterized by gliosis, is a prominent pathological feature of Alzheimer's disease (AD). This process involves the activation and proliferation of astrocytes and microglia. The recent identification of AD risk genes, such as TREM2, predominantly expressed in glial cells, has intensified research into their role in disease pathogenesis. Pathogenic forms of tau and amyloid-beta (A β) instigate neuroinflammation and gliosis, while activated glia can reciprocally influence the production and aggregation of these proteins. Emerging evidence indicates that dysregulated microglial and astrocytic responses contribute significantly to AD initiation and progression. Consequently, modulating aberrant glial activation and targeting pro-inflammatory cytokines are considered promising therapeutic strategies for AD (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: This figure effectively represents glial cell pathology by showing the transition of normal, supportive glial cells into their activated, pathological states, leading to neuroinflammation and neuronal death.

6.1.8. Proteasomal Dysfunction in Alzheimer's Disease

The ubiquitin-proteasome system (UPS) is critical for maintaining cellular proteostasis by degrading misfolded or damaged proteins. Disruption of this system is implicated in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease (AD). The efficient clearance of aberrant protein aggregates, such as amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) and hyperphosphorylated tau, is essential for neuronal viability and is mediated by the UPS [47]. Post-mortem studies have consistently demonstrated reduced proteasome activity in AD brains, correlating with the accumulation of neuropathological hallmarks. The intricate relationship between hyperphosphorylated tau and UPS dysfunction is evident, with evidence suggesting that tau oligomerization may inhibit proteasome function. However, the precise temporal sequence and causal relationship between these two pathological processes remain to be fully elucidated [48]. To definitively establish the initiating event in UPS-mediated AD pathogenesis, further investigation using cellular models is required.

6.2 Genetic Mutation

Genetic factors have been established as pivotal determinants in the development of Alzheimer's disease (AD). Approximately 70% of AD cases exhibit a genetic component. Early-onset AD (EOAD) is predominantly inherited in an autosomal dominant manner, with mutations in genes such as amyloid precursor protein (APP), presenilin-1 (PSEN1), presenilin-2 (PSEN2), and apolipoprotein E (APOE) identified as associated risk factors [49].

6.2.1. Amyloid Precursor Protein (APP)

The APP gene, located on chromosome 21, encodes a type I transmembrane protein that undergoes cleavage by α -, β -, and γ -secretases to generate amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) and other peptides. Over 30 mutations in the APP gene are associated with Alzheimer's disease (AD), primarily linked to $A\beta$ accumulation. Notably, a protective mutation, A673T, reduces $A\beta$ secretion, lowering AD risk [50]. Most APP mutations cluster near secretase cleavage sites. The KM670/671NL mutation increases amyloid plaque formation in the hippocampus and cortex, though without neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs). Mutations like A673V, D678H, and E682K are linked to cortical and hippocampal atrophy. Some mutations, such as A673V, also show NFTs, microglial activation, and neuronal loss. Mutations like V717I and V717L elevate the $A\beta_{42}/A\beta_{40}$ ratio by altering γ -secretase cleavage. Others, such as E693K and

A692G, disrupt α -secretase processing, forming aggregates that damage cellular membranes. The E693-delta deletion is linked to increased synaptotoxic $A\beta$ production [51].

6.2.2. Presenilin-1 (PSEN1) and Presenilin-2 (PSEN2)

PSEN1 and PSEN2, located on chromosomes 14 and 1 respectively, are homologous proteins sharing 67% similarity. While over 200 mutations have been identified in PSEN1, PSEN2 mutations are considerably rarer. PSEN1, as a core component of the γ -secretase complex, plays a pivotal role in $A\beta$ generation from APP [52]. Knockout studies in murine models have demonstrated synaptic dysfunction and memory impairment, highlighting the critical function of PSEN1 in neuronal and cognitive health. PSEN1 mutations predominantly involve single amino acid substitutions, with severe mutations characterized by the substitution of two amino acids. These mutations are associated with an increased $A\beta_{42}/A\beta_{40}$ ratio due to decreased $A\beta_{40}$ levels. In contrast, PSEN2 mutations exert a more limited impact on $A\beta$ production. However, certain PSEN2 mutations can significantly elevate γ -secretase activity and the $A\beta_{42}/A\beta_{40}$ ratio, contributing to familial AD pathogenesis [53].

6.2.3. Apolipoprotein E (APOE)

APOE, a glycoprotein primarily expressed in the liver and brain, functions as a ligand for lipoprotein particles, facilitating cholesterol transport and myelin production. The APOE gene, located on chromosome 19, exhibits three isoforms (APOE2, APOE3, and APOE4) due to single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). The APOE ϵ 4 allele is strongly associated with an increased risk for both early-onset and late-onset AD, while APOE ϵ 2 and APOE ϵ 3 alleles are linked to reduced risk or protective effects. APOE ϵ 4 has been implicated in $A\beta$ deposition as senile plaques and cerebral amyloid angiopathy, and is associated

with vascular damage within the brain, contributing to AD pathogenesis [54].

6.2.4. ATP-binding cassette transporter A1 (ABCA1)

ATP-binding cassette transporter A1 (ABCA1) regulates cholesterol efflux to circulation via ApoAI and to the brain via ApoE, playing a crucial role in ApoE lipidation and HDL biogenesis. Its functions are vital in atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease. In Alzheimer's disease (AD) models, ABCA1 deficiency increases amyloid plaques and reduces ApoE lipidation. Mutations in the ABCA1 gene cause Tangier disease, marked by low HDL and ApoAI levels, cholesterol accumulation, and heightened AD risk, underscoring ABCA1's importance in lipid metabolism and neurodegenerative disease pathogenesis [55].

6.2.5. Clusterin (CLU) and Bridging Integrator 1 (BIN1)

Unlike mutations in PSEN1, PSEN2, and APP, which cause early-onset Alzheimer's disease (EOAD), the CLU and BIN1 genes are key risk factors for late-onset Alzheimer's disease (LOAD). Genome-wide association studies (2009) identified CLU, located on chromosome 8, as upregulated in the cortex, hippocampus, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and plasma of AD patients, suggesting its role as a potential biomarker. CLU influences AD pathogenesis by either promoting or inhibiting amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) clearance, depending on $A\beta$ ratios. BIN1, a BAR domain adaptor protein, regulates membrane curvature and endocytosis. Multiple BIN1 isoforms exist in the brain, interacting with clathrin, synaptojanin, and amphiphysin 1, and regulating synaptic vesicle endocytosis. As the second most significant LOAD risk factor after ApoE, BIN1 contributes to $A\beta$ production and modulates tau pathology and neurofibrillary tangle formation [56].

6.2.6. Evolutionarily Conserved Signalling Intermediate in Toll Pathway (ECSIT)

The ECSIT gene on chromosome 19 is a genetic risk factor for Alzheimer's disease (AD). Its protein stabilizes mitochondrial respiratory complexes and regulates nuclear transcription factors, including NF- κ B, IRFs, and AP-1. ECSIT integrates pathways related to immunity (TLR), growth factors (TGF- β), and bone morphogenesis (BMP). It interacts with mitochondrial proteins LONP1 and GCDH for proteolysis and redox signaling, respectively, and AD-related genes ApoE, PSEN1, and PSEN2, linking oxidative stress, inflammation, and mitochondrial dysfunction in AD [57].

6.2.7. Estrogen Receptor Gene (ESR)

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is more prevalent in women, with more severe cognitive decline than men, partly due to the ApoE4 allele and hormonal changes post-menopause. Estrogen, known for its neuroprotective effects, acts via estrogen receptors (ER α and ER β) encoded on chromosomes 6 and 14, respectively. ER α and ER β show distinct brain distributions, influencing hypothalamic and hippocampal functions. Genetic variants like PvuII and XbaI SNPs in ER α and multiple ER β SNPs are linked to increased AD risk and cognitive impairment, underscoring their roles in modulating estrogen's effects in women [58].

7. Current Therapeutic Options

7.1. Dietary Management

Nutritional Interventions for Early-Stage Alzheimer's Disease Patients:

In the early stages of Alzheimer's disease (AD), nutritional interventions are designed with two primary objectives. Firstly, the prevention of weight loss, a common and harmful symptom of the disease, is prioritized through comprehensive dietary support for patients and caregivers. Secondly, efforts are directed at mitigating synaptic degeneration, a key pathological process associated with cognitive decline. This is achieved

by optimizing nutrient intake, often through the inclusion of specific dietary components, to decelerate synaptic loss and preserve cognitive functions [59]. Research increasingly highlights the potential of certain nutrients to address AD pathology by promoting neurogenesis and enhancing synaptic plasticity. Nutrients such as choline, docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), and uridine monophosphate have been shown to support synaptic health in AD. Choline, as a precursor to acetylcholine, holds particular promise. Although synthesized by the body, optimal levels require dietary intake, primarily from phosphatidylcholine, which is capable of crossing the blood-brain barrier to deliver choline to the brain. Citicoline, a bioavailable choline form, has demonstrated benefits in cerebrovascular diseases, including those related to dementia. Short-term studies have suggested potential improvements in attention and memory among older adults with cognitive impairments, but extended, rigorously designed clinical trials are needed to fully understand the long-term effects of choline supplementation on cognitive function in AD [60]. DHA, an essential fatty acid integral to cell membrane structure and function, plays a crucial role in the nervous system by supporting neurogenesis and overall neural health. Supplementation of DHA is often recommended for individuals with cognitive decline, as imbalances in its intake can negatively impact cellular homeostasis. DHA is primarily derived from sources such as fish, algae, and krill. In some markets, dietary supplements enriched with omega-3 fatty acids (EPA and DHA), choline, phospholipids, and essential vitamins, along with selenium, have been developed. These supplements are designed to enhance phospholipid synthesis in the brain, crucial for neuronal health. Preliminary findings suggest that such supplements may promote increased dendritic

spine density and synaptic protein levels, both of which are vital for synapse formation and neuronal connectivity [61].

Nutritional Interventions for Middle-Stage Alzheimer's Disease Patients:

In the moderate stages of AD, cognitive and behavioral deterioration poses significant challenges to nutritional intake. Patients often exhibit reduced interest in food, difficulty feeding themselves due to impaired motor skills, and altered appetites or food preferences. These issues frequently lead to malnutrition and weight loss, requiring caregivers to provide constant supervision during meals, which can be physically and emotionally taxing [62]. Feeding challenges, such as apraxia, hinder motor planning and execution necessary for self-feeding. Hand-feeding and the use of finger foods are practical strategies that can enhance mealtime success and maintain nutritional intake. Additionally, cognitive impairments like visual agnosia, which affects the ability to recognize food or utensils, further complicate feeding. Clear verbal and physical guidance, including hand-over-hand assistance, can help address these challenges and reduce mealtime frustrations [63]. Weight loss, common across all stages of dementia, is often exacerbated by agitation and other behavioral disturbances, which disrupt eating patterns and increase caregiver burden. Addressing these issues through targeted interventions, such as adequate protein and caloric intake, is crucial. Protein is particularly important for maintaining muscle mass, with emerging evidence suggesting that older adults require 1.5 g/kg per day to achieve positive nitrogen balance and promote muscle growth [64]. Oral nutritional supplements (ONS) are effective in addressing malnutrition in individuals with mild to moderate dementia. By providing essential macronutrients and micronutrients, ONS contribute to weight

maintenance, improve anthropometric measures, and may enhance immune function. Clinical studies have consistently supported their role as a valuable therapeutic tool for managing the nutritional needs of this population [65].

Nutritional Interventions for Later-Stage Alzheimer's Disease Patients:

In advanced stages of AD, patients often experience significant physical and physiological decline, including weakened oral and tongue muscles that impair chewing, as well as a diminished sense of taste and smell. Dysphagia, a complex swallowing disorder, is a common issue at this stage, resulting in restricted food choices, malnutrition, and dehydration. Medications that alter saliva production can further contribute to oral sensitivity and exacerbate swallowing difficulties [66]. Dysphagia requires a multidisciplinary approach involving physicians, speech therapists, nutritionists, and nurses to ensure accurate diagnosis and effective management. Clinical indicators such as coughing, choking, and feeding difficulties, along with functional assessments, are utilized to identify swallowing disorders. Food consistency often needs modification, with thickening agents used to enhance texture while maintaining nutritional value. Collaboration between speech therapists and nutritionists is essential to achieve an optimal balance between safety and nutritional adequacy [67,68]. Dietary supplements can complement modified meals by providing essential nutrients and increasing caloric intake. Strategies such as these are crucial in managing the nutritional needs of advanced AD patients, improving their overall health and quality of life.

Nutritional approaches in different phases:

Mild Phase	Moderate Phase	Severe Phase
Preserving cellular membrane health and rectifying nutritional imbalances	Addressing behavioral changes, weight loss, and dysphagia in Alzheimer's patients through nutritional interventions. Evaluating ONS for weight management and identify early dysphagia indicators.	Developing appropriate management strategies for dysphagia, addressing weight loss through potential oral nutritional supplement (ONS) intervention, and mitigating the risk of pulmonary aspiration, which may necessitate ear, nose, and throat (ENT) evaluation.

7.2. Enzyme Replacement Therapy: Beta-Secretase (BACE1) Inhibition

The inhibition of beta-secretase (BACE1) has been identified as a promising therapeutic strategy for Alzheimer's disease (AD). BACE1 plays a pivotal role in generating amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) peptides, toxic fragments that accumulate in the brain and form senile plaques, a hallmark of AD pathology. These plaques are closely linked to neuronal damage and cognitive decline. By inhibiting BACE1, the cascade leading to $A\beta$ production can potentially be interrupted, offering hope for therapies targeting the underlying mechanisms of AD progression [69]. Small molecule inhibitors have been extensively explored as a means to inhibit BACE1. These compounds bind to the enzyme's active site, thereby blocking its ability to cleave amyloid precursor protein (APP) and reducing $A\beta$ production. Although preclinical studies demonstrated their efficacy in lowering $A\beta$ levels, their clinical application has faced significant hurdles. Drugs like verubecestat, lanabecestat, and elenbecestat, despite reducing $A\beta$ levels, failed to provide notable cognitive benefits or exhibited unfavorable safety profiles [70]. These challenges underscore the complexities of BACE1 inhibition and highlight the necessity for innovative approaches to overcome the limitations observed in previous clinical trials. Biological inhibitors, including

antibody-based therapies and peptide inhibitors, offer alternative strategies for targeting BACE1. While antibodies can provide highly specific enzyme targeting, their large molecular size and difficulty crossing the blood-brain barrier have limited their success. Peptide inhibitors, designed to mimic BACE1's natural substrates, may achieve better brain penetration and offer potential advantages. However, their effectiveness in humans remains under investigation, and overcoming delivery and efficacy challenges is essential for the advancement of these therapies [71]. RNA interference (RNAi) provides a genetic approach to reducing BACE1 expression. By employing small interfering RNA (siRNA) to degrade BACE1 mRNA, enzyme levels and $A\beta$ production can be diminished. Nevertheless, challenges related to crossing the blood-brain barrier, ensuring specific neuronal uptake, and mitigating off-target effects pose significant obstacles. Innovative delivery mechanisms and a deeper understanding of siRNA functionality within the brain will be crucial for translating this approach into viable treatments [72,73]. CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing offers a transformative method for addressing BACE1 at the genetic level. By selectively inactivating or downregulating the BACE1 gene, this technology can theoretically prevent enzyme production and reduce $A\beta$ accumulation at its source. Despite its potential,

challenges such as efficient neuronal delivery, off-target effects, and the permanent nature of genetic modifications necessitate thorough preclinical evaluation and clinical trials. Additionally, ethical considerations regarding human genetic editing must be carefully navigated within robust regulatory frameworks [74].

Gamma-Secretase Inhibition

Gamma-secretase inhibition serves as another approach to targeting the amyloid cascade in AD. This enzyme complex is essential for the final cleavage of APP, leading to the production of A β peptides, including the highly aggregation-prone A β 42. By inhibiting gamma-secretase, the generation of A β species can be reduced, potentially alleviating the toxic effects of A β accumulation and plaque formation. While preclinical studies have demonstrated reductions in A β levels, issues related to drug selectivity and adverse effects have complicated clinical development. Nonetheless, further investigation into selective and tolerable inhibitors is warranted [75]. Small molecule inhibitors targeting gamma-secretase aim to block the enzyme's cleavage of APP. Although compounds such as semagacestat successfully reduced A β levels, their clinical development was halted due to side effects, including cognitive decline. More selective inhibitors, such as avagacestat, have also faced challenges, highlighting the intricate nature of targeting gamma-secretase for AD treatment [76]. Gamma-secretase modulators (GSMs) provide a nuanced alternative by selectively modulating enzyme activity rather than completely inhibiting it. GSMs focus on reducing the production of toxic A β species, such as A β 42, while promoting less harmful variants like A β 38. This approach preserves gamma-secretase's essential physiological roles, reducing the likelihood of unintended side effects. While earlier modulators, such as tarenflurbil, did not meet clinical expectations, ongoing research aims to develop

more effective GSMs with improved selectivity and therapeutic outcomes. This refined strategy holds promise for achieving a balance between efficacy and safety in targeting gamma-secretase for AD [77].

7.3 Gene Therapy

Gene therapy is recognized as a cutting-edge approach for addressing Alzheimer's disease (AD), a progressive neurodegenerative condition characterized by cognitive decline and memory loss. Unlike traditional treatments that focus primarily on alleviating symptoms, gene therapy targets the genetic and molecular underpinnings of the disease, offering potential to modify its trajectory and slow progression. This approach aims to address AD at its root cause, distinguishing it from conventional therapeutic strategies [78]. Gene-editing technologies, including the CRISPR-Cas9 system, allow for precise alterations to genes involved in AD pathology. Specific targets include the amyloid precursor protein (APP) and presenilin genes (PSEN1 and PSEN2), which are central to the production and accumulation of amyloid-beta plaques—a defining feature of the disease. Strategies such as reducing APP expression have shown promise in decreasing amyloid-beta production, thereby slowing plaque formation and neurodegeneration. Such targeted genetic interventions hold potential for significant advancements in AD treatment [79]. Another promising aspect of gene therapy involves delivering neurotrophic factors like nerve growth factor (NGF) and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) to the brain. These proteins play critical roles in maintaining neuronal survival, growth, and function. By introducing genes encoding these factors, neuronal loss and synaptic dysfunction—key contributors to AD symptoms—may be mitigated. This therapeutic strategy is aimed at improving synaptic plasticity, enhancing cognitive function, and delaying disease progression [80]. Anti-amyloid strategies

are also under investigation, focusing on introducing genes that encode therapeutic proteins capable of degrading amyloid-beta plaques. These proteins include antibodies that bind to amyloid-beta, promoting its clearance via immune mechanisms or enzymatic degradation to non-toxic fragments. Such approaches are being explored to reduce the toxic burden of amyloid plaques and interrupt the cascade of pathological events in AD. Microglial modulation through gene

therapy offers additional potential. Microglia, the brain's immune cells, contribute to both the development and progression of AD pathology. By introducing genes that influence microglial activity, it may be possible to enhance their ability to clear amyloid plaques and tau tangles while reducing neuroinflammation. This strategy aims to restore a protective microglial phenotype, thereby supporting neuronal health and slowing disease progression [81,82].

Table 1: The methods for neurotrophic factor delivery in Alzheimer's disease.

Method	Description	Example/applications	Advantages	Challenges	Reference
Viral Vectors	Uses modified viruses to deliver genes encoding neurotrophic factors.	AAV vectors delivering NGF or BDNF genes to specific brain regions.	Long-term expression of neurotrophic factors.	Potential immune response and off-target effects.	[82]
Direct Protein Infusion	Direct administration of neurotrophic factors into the brain or CSF.	ICV infusion of NGF; CED to distribute neurotrophic factors in brain tissue.	Provides immediate therapeutic effects.	Invasive; requires surgery and carries infection risks.	[80]
Encapsulated Cell Biodelivery	Implantation of genetically modified cells that secrete neurotrophic factors.	NGF-secreting cells encapsulated and implanted in the basal forebrain.	Continuous delivery; reduces need for repeated interventions.	Invasive; potential immune rejection of encapsulated cells.	[83]
Nanoparticle-Based Delivery	Use of nanoparticles or liposomes to encapsulate and deliver neurotrophic factors.	Nanoparticles delivering BDNF across the BBB.	Non-invasive; targets specific brain regions.	Ensuring stability and effective crossing of the BBB.	[84]

Symptomatic Treatment

Symptomatic treatments for AD primarily address cognitive and behavioral symptoms, including memory impairment, confusion, and mood disturbances. These therapies, such as cholinesterase inhibitors and NMDA receptor antagonists, provide temporary relief without altering the underlying disease mechanisms [84].

Behavioural symptoms like aggression and agitation are often managed with antipsychotics or mood stabilizers. Alongside pharmacological options, non-drug interventions—such as cognitive training, physical exercise, and social activities—play a crucial role in improving patients' quality of life and supporting caregivers [85,86].

Table 2: Symptomatic treatment of Alzheimer’s Disease:

Category	Medication/ Intervention	Mechanism of action	Symptoms addressed	Common side effects	Reference
Cholinesterase inhibitors	Donepezil, Rivastigmine, Galantamine	Inhibit acetylcholinesterase, increasing acetylcholine levels	Memory loss, confusion, cognitive decline	Nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, muscle cramps	[87]
NMDA Receptor Antagonists	Memantine	Blocks NMDA receptors, reducing glutamate-induced excitotoxicity	Moderate to severe cognitive symptoms	Dizziness, headache, constipation	[88]
Antidepressants	Sertraline, Citalopram	SSRIs increase serotonin levels in the brain	Depression, anxiety, irritability	Nausea, dry mouth, drowsiness	[89]
Antipsychotics	Risperidone, Olanzapine	Block dopamine receptors, reducing psychotic symptoms	Aggression, hallucinations, delusions	Increased risk of stroke, sedation, weight gain	[90]
Anxiolytics	Lorazepam, Diazepam	Enhance GABA activity, producing calming effects	Anxiety, restlessness	Drowsiness, dizziness, dependency risk	[89]
Cognitive enhancers	Cognitive therapy, Reminiscence therapy	Non-pharmacological interventions to stimulate cognitive function	Cognitive decline, memory issues	Minimal physical side effects	[91]
Antioxidants	Vitamin E, Selegiline	Reduces oxidative stress to protect neurons	Slows progression of symptoms	Diarrhea, fatigue, increased bleeding risk	[92]
Anti-inflammatory drugs	NSAIDs (Aspirin, Ibuprofen)	Reduce inflammation that might contribute to neurodegeneration	Potential cognitive symptoms, inflammation	Gastrointestinal issues, bleeding risks	[93]

Fig 7: This figure illustrates the efficacy of various allopathic medicines used in the treatment of Alzheimer’s Disease

Table 3: List of the medicinal plants used in the treatment of Alzheimer's Disease:

Herbal Plant	Pharmacological Mechanism of Action	Receptors Involved	Main Phytoconstituent	Parts Used	Recommended Dose Regimen	References
Ginkgo biloba	Enhances cholinergic function, antioxidant activity, reduces β -amyloid plaques	Cholinergic receptors, NMDA	Flavonoids, Terpenoids	Leaves	120-240 mg/day (divided doses)	[94]
Bacopa monnieri	Enhances cognitive function, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	Cholinergic receptors	Bacosides	Whole plant	300-450 mg/day (standardized extract)	[95]
Panax ginseng	Neuroprotective, enhances cholinergic neurotransmission, anti-inflammatory	Cholinergic receptors, NMDA	Ginsenosides	Roots	200-400 mg/day	[95]
Withania somnifera (Ashwagandha)	Reduces β -amyloid plaques, antioxidant, enhances cholinergic function	Cholinergic receptors	Withanolides	Roots, leaves	300-500 mg/day	[69]
Salvia officinalis (Sage)	Inhibits AChE, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	Cholinergic receptors	Rosmarinic acid, Flavonoids	Leaves	300-600 mg/day (standardized extract)	[94]
Curcuma longa (Turmeric)	Reduces β -amyloid plaques, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	Amyloid precursor protein (APP)	Curcumin	Rhizome	400-600 mg/day (standardized extract)	[96]
Centella asiatica (Gotu Kola)	Enhances cognitive function, antioxidant, neuroprotective	Cholinergic receptors	Asiaticoside, Madecassoside	Whole plant	500-1000 mg/day	[97]
Huperzia serrata	Inhibits AChE, enhances cognitive function	Cholinergic receptors	Huperzine A	Whole plant	50-200 mcg/day	[95]
Rhodiola rosea	Enhances cognitive function, antioxidant, anti-fatigue	Cholinergic receptors	Rosavin, Salidroside	Roots	200-600 mg/day	[98]
Melissa officinalis (Lemon Balm)	Inhibits AChE, antioxidant, neuroprotective	Cholinergic receptors	Rosmarinic acid	Leaves	300-600 mg/day	[96]
Crocus sativus (Saffron)	Inhibits AChE, reduces β -amyloid aggregation, antioxidant	Cholinergic receptors, NMDA	Crocin, Safranal	Stigmas	30 mg/day	[99]
Camellia sinensis (Green Tea)	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, reduces β -amyloid plaques	Amyloid precursor protein (APP)	Epigallocatechin gallate	Leaves	300-500 mg/day (standardized extract)	[94]

Zingiber officinale (Ginger)	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective	Cholinergic receptors	Gingerol, Shogaol	Rhizome	500-1000 mg/day	[98]
Rosmarinus officinalis (Rosemary)	Inhibits AChE, antioxidant, enhances memory function	Cholinergic receptors	Carnosic acid, Rosmarinic acid	Leaves	200-400 mg/day (standardized extract)	[96]
Galanthus nivalis (Snowdrop)	Inhibits AChE, enhances cognitive function	Cholinergic receptors	Galantamine	Bulbs	8-24 mg/day (standardized extract)	[97]

Fig 8: This figure illustrates the efficacy of various herbal medicines used in the treatment of Alzheimer’s Disease.

Table 4: List of the marketed formulation used in the treatment of Alzheimer’s Disease:

Product Name	Brand Name	Pharmacological Mechanism of Action	Receptors Involved	Main Phytoconstituent	Parts Used	References
Ginkgol d	Nature's Way	Enhances cholinergic function, antioxidant activity, reduces β -amyloid plaques	Cholinergic receptors, NMDA	Flavonoids, Terpenoids	Leaves	[100]
Brahmi Bacopa	Himalaya Herbal Healthcare	Enhances cognitive function, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	Cholinergic receptors	Bacosides	Whole plant	[101]
Ginseng Complex	Solgar	Neuroprotective, enhances cholinergic neurotransmission, anti-inflammatory	Cholinergic receptors, NMDA	Ginsenosides	Roots	[102]

Ashwagandha Capsules	Organic India	Reduces β -amyloid plaques, antioxidant, enhances cholinergic function	Cholinergic receptors	Withanolides	Roots, leaves	[103]
Sage Memory Focus	Natures Aid	Inhibits AChE, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	Cholinergic receptors	Rosmarinic acid, Flavonoids	Leaves	[100]
Curcumin 95	Doctor's Best	Reduces β -amyloid plaques, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	Amyloid precursor protein (APP)	Curcumin	rhizome	[102]
Gotu Kola Capsules	Nature's Answer	Enhances cognitive function, antioxidant, neuroprotective	Cholinergic receptors	Asiaticoside, Madecassoside	Whole plant	[102]
Huperzine A	Source Naturals	Inhibits AChE, enhances cognitive function	Cholinergic receptors	Huperzine A	Whole plant	[103]
Rhodiola Rosea Extract	NOW Foods	Enhances cognitive function, antioxidant, anti-fatigue	Cholinergic receptors	Rosavin, Salidroside	Roots	[101]
Lemon Balm (Melissa)	Nature's Way	Inhibits AChE, antioxidant, neuroprotective	Cholinergic receptors	Rosmarinic acid	Leaves	[100]
Saffron Extract	Life Extension	Inhibits AChE, reduces β -amyloid aggregation, antioxidant	Cholinergic receptors, NMDA	Crocin, Safranal	Stigmas	[101]
Green Tea Extract	Jarrow Formulas	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, reduces β -amyloid plaques	Amyloid precursor protein (APP)	Epigallocatechin gallate	Leaves	[100]
Ginger Root	Nature's Way	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective	Cholinergic receptors	Gingerol, Shogaol	Rhizome	[103]
Rosemary Extract	Nature's Answer	Inhibits AChE, antioxidant, enhances memory function	Cholinergic receptors	Carnosic acid, Rosmarinic acid	Leaves	[102]
Galantamine	Reminyl	Inhibits AChE, enhances cognitive function	Cholinergic receptors	Galantamine	Bulbs	[100]

RESULTS:

A comprehensive overview of Alzheimer's disease (AD) is presented, emphasizing epidemiology, clinical manifestations, and risk factors. Key discussions include the pathophysiology, cellular and molecular mechanisms, and genetic mutations driving AD progression. Current therapeutic

options are analyzed, along with their limitations, and emerging strategies like dietary management and gene therapy are explored. The interplay of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors in AD development is highlighted, underscoring the need for further research to develop effective treatments and enhance understanding of the disease's underlying mechanisms.

CONCLUSION:

Alzheimer's disease (AD) represents a significant challenge in modern medicine, affecting millions of individuals worldwide and imposing a substantial burden on healthcare systems. Despite extensive research over the past decades, the precise etiology of AD remains incompletely understood, with complex interactions among genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors contributing to its onset and progression. Current therapeutic approaches primarily focus on symptomatic relief, particularly targeting the cholinergic and glutamatergic systems. However, these interventions offer only modest benefits and do not alter the underlying disease process. The exploration of novel therapeutic targets, including β -amyloid plaques, tau tangles, neuroinflammation, oxidative stress, and mitochondrial dysfunction, holds promise for more effective treatment strategies. Additionally, the increasing interest in non-pharmacological approaches, such as lifestyle interventions, cognitive training, and diet, highlights the importance of a holistic approach to AD management. The potential of herbal medicinal plants and formulations in the treatment of AD offers a promising avenue, with several phytoconstituents demonstrating neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. These natural compounds, often targeting multiple pathological pathways simultaneously, provide an alternative or complementary approach to conventional therapies. However, rigorous clinical

trials are necessary to establish their efficacy, safety, and optimal dosing regimens.

Conflict Of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. This review article was conducted solely for academic and research purposes, with no financial or personal relationships influencing the content presented.

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